

Shakhova Olga
Associate Professor, Department of Paediatrics and Paediatric Infectious Diseases Bukovinian State Medical University
Chernivtsi, Ukraine
6th year students
Kalashnikov Vadym
Danyliuk Vladyslav

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17599816>

METHODS OF NON-INVASIVE LUNG VENTILATION IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE RESPIRATORY FAILURE (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Abstract:

Acute respiratory failure is a pathological condition in which gas exchange is impaired, leading to further complications. Non-invasive lung ventilation plays a leading role in modern paediatric practice as an effective method of maintaining respiration in children with various forms of acute and chronic respiratory failure. Unlike invasive artificial lung ventilation, non-invasive ventilation does not use endotracheal intubation, which reduces ventilator-associated complications. The main goal of non-invasive ventilation is to ensure adequate gas exchange, improve oxygenation, and reduce the work of the respiratory muscles. Methods of non-invasive ventilation include high-flow nasal cannula therapy (HFNC), continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) and bilevel positive airway pressure (BPAP).

Keywords: acute respiratory failure, invasive lung ventilation, non-invasive lung ventilation, high-flow nasal cannula therapy

Materials and methods: We conducted a review of the current literature based on articles published in PubMed databases over the past 10 years. Information on methods of non-invasive lung ventilation in paediatrics was analysed.

The aim - was to analyse literary sources and studies and to identify methods of non-invasive lung ventilation in paediatrics.

Relevance: Acute respiratory failure is a pathological condition in which the respiratory system cannot provide adequate gas exchange in the body, resulting in hypoxaemia and hypercapnia. According to statistics, the mortality rate of children with severe respiratory failure ranges from 11 to 34% [1].

Respiratory support remains the most common intervention performed in paediatric intensive care units. Respiratory support can be divided into invasive and non-invasive. The presence of complications during and after invasive mechanical ventilation has led to the widespread use of non-invasive methods of respiratory support in children with acute respiratory diseases [2].

Non-invasive ventilation is used to provide ventilation support and increase gas exchange at the alveolar level without the use of an invasive artificial airway, such as an endotracheal tube or tracheostomy. Indications for non-invasive ventilation range from acute hypoxic respiratory failure in the intensive care unit or emergency department to chronic respiratory failure in patients with neuromuscular diseases. Contraindications to the use of non-invasive ventilation include reduced or absent consciousness, apnoea, severe respiratory distress, and inability to maintain upper airway patency [3].

Results and discussion: Non-invasive ventilation methods include high-flow nasal cannula therapy (HFNC), continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) and bilevel positive airway pressure (BPAP) [2,4,5].

HFNC has become a popular method of non-invasive respiratory support in paediatric intensive care units due to its ease of use, greater comfort for patients, and the ability to transfer patients still receiving HFNC to the therapeutic ward. Currently, HFNC is often used as a first-line method for respiratory support in diseases such as bronchiolitis, bronchial asthma, pneumonia, and heart failure [2].

HFNO delivers humidified and heated oxygen at a rate of 2 to 70 L/min through special nasal cannulas, with flow rates determined by patient weight and clinical needs. HFNO can be useful as a method of preoxygenation in infants and children, prolonging the time of apnoea before desaturation, but in children with reduced minute ventilation or apnoea, HFNO does not improve alveolar gas exchange [3].

The basic principle of HFNC is to establish a higher oxygen flow than the inspiratory flow, which leads to upper airway washout, reduced nasal resistance, and reduced dead space. HFNC also induces positive pressure in the airways, leading to alveolar recruitment of collapsed lesions and an increase in functional residual capacity. In addition, HFNC reduces the influx of ambient air, minimises dilution of the desired gas composition, and improves oxygenation [6].

Depending on the patient's weight, HFNC flow, and the size of the nasal cannulae relative to the nostrils, HFNC is associated with the generation of positive pressure at the end of exhalation. The amount of positive pressure generated at the end of exhalation is also influenced by the degree of leakage through the oral cavity. It has been found that in premature infants, HFNC can generate positive distending pressure similar to CPAP pressure and therefore treat apnoea in premature infants.

The mechanism of action of CPAP involves the use of constant expiratory pressure applied to the air-

ways at a constant level. On the other hand, BPAP provides two different types of pressure: higher pressure during inhalation and lower pressure during exhalation, which facilitates inhalation and reduces the work of the respiratory muscles. Like CPAP, expiratory positive airway pressure during BPAP helps to relieve upper airway obstruction and recruit the lungs, leading to improved gas exchange, thereby reducing ventilation-perfusion mismatch and improving oxygenation and carbon dioxide clearance. In addition, BPAP devices have a backup respiratory rate option to ensure that a minimum respiratory rate is maintained in cases where respiratory effort is insufficient.

When comparing CPAP and HFNC, it was found that both are associated with improved respiratory function, but CPAP was superior in the treatment of children with more severe respiratory failure. HFNC should be used to treat children with milder or less severe forms of respiratory failure [4,5].

Conclusion: Thus, in paediatric practice, HFNC, CPAP and BPAP are the most commonly used non-invasive methods of lung ventilation. When comparing CPAP and HFNC, it was found that CPAP is more effective in treating children with severe respiratory failure.

References:

1. Weiss SL, Asaro LA, Flori HR, Allen GL, Wypij D, Curley MA; Randomized Evaluation of Sedation Titration for Respiratory Failure (RESTORE) Study Investigators. Multiple Organ Dysfunction in Children Mechanically Ventilated for Acute Respiratory Failure. *Pediatr Crit Care Med*. 2017 Apr;18(4):319-329. doi: 10.1097/PCC.0000000000001091. PMID: 28212163; PMCID: PMC5380520.

2. Ramnarayan P, Richards-Belle A, Drikite L, Saull M, Orzechowska I, Darnell R, Sadique Z, Lester

J, Morris KP, Tume LN, Davis PJ, Peters MJ, Feltbower RG, Grieve R, Thomas K, Mouncey PR, Harrison DA, Rowan KM; FIRST-ABC Step-Up RCT Investigators and the Paediatric Critical Care Society Study Group. Effect of High-Flow Nasal Cannula Therapy vs Continuous Positive Airway Pressure Therapy on Liberation From Respiratory Support in Acutely Ill Children Admitted to Pediatric Critical Care Units: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA*. 2022 Jul 12;328(2):162-172. doi: 10.1001/jama.2022.9615. PMID: 35707984; PMCID: PMC9204623.

3. Sequera-Ramos L, Garcia-Marcinkiewicz A, Riva T, Fuchs A. Noninvasive ventilation in children: A review for the pediatric anesthesiologist. *Paediatr Anaesth*. 2022 Feb;32(2):262-272. doi: 10.1111/pan.14364. Epub 2021 Dec 14. PMID: 34877751.

4. Al-Mukhaini KS, Al-Rahbi NM. Noninvasive Ventilation and High-Flow Nasal Cannulae Therapy for Children with Acute Respiratory Failure: An overview. *Sultan Qaboos Univ Med J*. 2018 Aug;18(3):e278-e285. doi: 10.18295/squmj.2018.18.03.003. Epub 2018 Dec 19. PMID: 30607266; PMCID: PMC6307645.

5. Wang Z, He Y, Zhang X, Luo Z. Non-Invasive Ventilation Strategies in Children With Acute Lower Respiratory Infection: A Systematic Review and Bayesian Network Meta-Analysis. *Front Pediatr*. 2021 Dec 2;9:749975. doi: 10.3389/fped.2021.749975. PMID: 34926341; PMCID: PMC8677331.

6. Kwon JW. High-flow nasal cannula oxygen therapy in children: a clinical review. *Clin Exp Pediatr*. 2020 Jan;63(1):3-7. doi: 10.3345/kjp.2019.00626. Epub 2019 Oct 28. PMID: 31999912; PMCID: PMC7027347.